

Qard on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research

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Abstract

This research aims to map research topics surrounding the Qard contract on Islamic Financial Inclusion with a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the key word "Qard" within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around the Qard contract based on the journals that have been collected. The research results show that There are 7 mapping research topics surrounding the Qard contract, namely: (1) Application of the Qard contract; (2) The influence of the Qard contract; (3) Juridical study of Qard contracts; (4) Efforts to develop the Qard contract; (5) Public perception of the Qard contract; (6) Factors that influence public interest in the Qard contract; and (7) Other issues related to the Qard contract. The implication and contribution of this research is mapping research topics surrounding the Qard contract, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: Qard; Islamic Financial Inclusion; Library Research; VOSviewer; Bibliometrics

Introduction

Islam has the principle of mutual assistance in improving the economy of the people, one of which is the use of Qard contracts regarding debts and receivables. Apart from being an instrument of the tabarru' / mutual assistance agreement, the Qard contract also differentiates between loan funds at Sharia Financial Institutions and loan funds at Conventional Financial Institutions. In Sharia Financial Institutions, funds in the form of money loans are not subject to interest which contains elements of usury. Thus, Sharia Financial Institutions must implement the principles of Qard contracts in accordance with the instructions taught by the Prophet sallallaahu 'Alaihi Wasallam. Sharia financial institutions have many funding models to serve customers, one of which is the Qard contract. The contract is in the form of capital that must be paid by the customer without any additions or interest. Thus, in practice, the Qard contract helps support the economy of communities ranging from lower class, middle class, to people who need assistance for their survival.

The aim of this research is to map research topics around Qard contracts in Islamic Financial Inclusion using library research. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding the Qard contract, so that it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this research is mapping

research topics surrounding the Qard contract, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Literature Review

Qard is a contract that provides funds or bills by Sharia Financial Institutions (muqridh) to customers (muqtaridh). Customers must pay their bills either in cash or in installments within a predetermined time period. The person who enters into a Qard contract is obliged to return the loan principal at the agreed time, and the management fee is charged to the customer. If the customer does not pay the debt at the specified maturity date, the Sharia Financial Institution can provide an extension of payment time or cancel half or all (amortized) of the responsibility (KHES, Chapter XXVII, Articles 606, 607, 610 and DSN-MUI Fatwa, No. 19/DSN-MUI/IV/2001).

Islamic Financial Inclusion refers to efforts to ensure that all individuals and economic entities, regardless of their economic, social, or geographic background, have fair and appropriate access to financial products and services that comply with sharia principles. Sharia principles are Islamic economic rules and guidelines that prohibit riba (interest), excessive speculation, and investment in businesses that are forbidden under Islamic law. Islamic Financial Inclusion includes a variety of financial products and services, such as savings, microfinance, insurance, investment and other financial instruments, that comply with sharia principles. The aim of Islamic Financial Inclusion is to increase public access to financial services that are in accordance with the values and principles of the Islamic religion. Islamic Financial Inclusion has a positive impact on the economy, including reducing poverty, improving community welfare, and strengthening financial system stability. Apart from that, Islamic Financial Inclusion also supports the development of the sharia financial sector as a whole, which involves financial institutions such as sharia banks, sharia insurance companies and sharia capital markets.

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of Library Research research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, Library Research research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and organize the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Methodolgy

This research uses a qualitative approach in the nature of a library research. The object of the research is the Qard contract. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles about Qard contracts in Islamic Financial Inclusion. The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the

key word " Qard " within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around the Qard contract based on the journals that have been collected.

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Qard Contracts in Sharia Financial Institutions

The results of scientific research regarding Qard contracts in sharia financial institutions during the period 2005 to 2022 show an increase in publications every year, especially in the last three years. We also obtained publication data in the form of articles totaling 122 titles from accredited national journals. In fact, in 2021, there will be 26 articles published. Thus, the average scientific publication regarding Qard contracts is 20 or more articles per year.

Table 1. Scientific publication data regarding the Qard contract by year

Year of Publication n	Number of Publication n Articles	Year of Publication n	Number of Publication n Articles	Year of Publication n	Number of Publication n Articles
2005	1	2015	5	2020	22
2011	2	2016	6	2021	26
2012	1	2017	7	2022	20
2013	1	2018	6		
2014	6	2019	18		
Total 122					

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2019.

In table 2, there are 11 affiliates or institutions that publish the most research articles regarding Qard contracts in sharia financial institutions. Justisia Ekonomika Journal: Master of Sharia Economic Law for Students at the University of Muhammadiyah Surabaya is the journal publishing institution that publishes the most research results regarding Qard contracts, with a total of 4 articles.

Table 2. Scientific journal publishing institutions regarding the Qard agreement

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Number of Publications
Journal of Justisia Ekonomika: Master of Sharia Economic Law	4
Management of Zakat and Waqf Journal (MAZAWA)	3
Al Maqashidi Journal (Nusantara Islamic Law Journal), Al-Amwal : (Journal of Islamic Economic Law), AL-FALAH (Journal of Islamic Economics), El Dinar (Shariah Finance	2

and Banking Journal), ISLAMIKA (Islamic Religious Education), Journal Law (IUS QUIA IUSTUM), Kanun (Journal of Legal Sciences), Ar-Ribhu (Journal of Sharia Management and Finance), Qiema Journal (Qomaruddin Islamic Economics Magazine).

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2019

The most productive researchers are: Awaluddin, Lian Fuad; Rohmah, Wahab, Ummi Nurjannah Prastyawati; Abdul, Cahyono, Eko Arief, Purwadi, Muhammad Imam, who wrote 2 journal articles. Meanwhile, other researchers only wrote 1 journal article about the Qard contract, namely: Abdillah, Yudi Khoeri, Abdullah, Rosmawati R.; M Wahyuddin, Abdussakur, Abdussakur, Aderemi Muhammad Shahrul Ifwat, Abdulmajeed Muhammad Raji; Ishak, Afif, Mufti, Afkar, Taudlikhul, Aini, Rukyal, Al-Banna, Achmad Nurdany; Hasan, Aris Ismail, Aris; Hannanong, Ash-shiddiqy, Muhammad, Astuti, Syamsuddin Bidol; Andi, Badriyah, Selly Sri Wulandari, Neni Nuraeni; Mila, Basoeki, Zendy Sellyfio Ardiana; Radityo Dewandaru, Bidol Andi, Syamsuddin; Astuti, Bimo, Asti Marlina; Muhamad Zakie Hanifan; Widhi Ariyo, Bimo, Asti Marlina; Muhamad Zakie Hanifan; Widhi Ariyo, Candra, Anggreany Hustia; Mister, Cholidah, Chusnul, Daningrum Mikhriani, Januar; Mikhriani, Dewi Fatmasari, Dini Widyarningsih, Fadly Kholil; Arif, Suyud, Fadly; Nawawi, Farhan, Ahmad Hendra Rofiulla; Eko Raharto;, LUFA, LUFA, Fatonah, Siti, Fatwa, Nurul, Filiawati, Kenlies Era Rosalina Marsudi; Sinta Garwautama Sulaeman; Noor, Iqbal, Paramadita Khalifa; Sulaeman Ghafur, Saifuddin Syuhri; Abd Halim, Mohamad Torik Langlang Buana; Sofyan Hamidi, Mohammad Hamka, Restu Nur Hakim; Muhammad Handoyo, Nurma Khusna Khanifa; Handoyo Hayati, Ilda, Hazmi, Faiqul, Hidayah, Taufiq Hidayati Agus, Nurul; Saron Hidayatina, Hidayatina Hidayatullah, Tri Hidayati; Muhammad Syarif HS, Moh Musfiq Arifqi & Dedi Eko Riyadi Huda, Bakhrul Humaira Mahfud., Dahlan Humaira, Humaira Husna, Sri Sudiarti; Julfan Saputra; Asmaul Isnarti, Baiq Joni, Alya Khairunnisa; Joni Juniwati, Salma Aulia Devyane; Kristeningsih Kristeningsih; Endang Hatma Karjuni, Yasin Yasin; Dwiya Endah Pandu Probowati; Barnawi Barnawi; Agus Khan, Farah Muneer; Foyasal Lucy Chairael Maivalinda, Fernanda Mahardika, Naura Mumtaz; Dewa Putra Kharisma Marlina, Zakaria Batubara; Eli Maulana Eva Theresna; Nurdiansyah, Dian Hakip, Dede Rapsanjani; Ruchjana Maulida Ahmadi; Umar, Masyitah, Sri; Hasan Melis, Saprida Saprida; Choiriyah Choiriyah; Melis MS, Nur Afni Hairuddin; Rafiuddin Ibrahim; Syaifullah, Muhayatsyah, Ali Muin, Abdul Muntaqo, Lutfan Muntaqo Musari, Khairunnisa Musyafa, Azizah Fatmawati; Rinata Maulidia; Muhammad Alwi Mutawali, Mutawali Nadia, Moh. Afif; Nasaruddin; Nugroho, Herjanriasto Bakti Nuraeni, Eneng Elyana; Jalaluddin Jalaluddin; Nuraeni Nurcholis, Ibn Khajar; Ahmad Hijri Alfian; Lutfi Pertiwi, Iza Hanifuddin; Siska Hana, Putra, Irhamsyah, Sugianto, Abi Waqqosh; Saparuddin Siregar; Sugianto Susanti, Muhammad Afani Adam; Ahmad Habibi; Alfina Shafira; Asmita Dewi Santi; Hafidz Kurniawan; Dian Nita Syafa'at, M Afnan Afandi; Abdul Kholiq Tajuddin, Wan Mohd Khairul Firdaus; Mahadi Bin Mohammad; Syed Mohd Azmi; Daud Ismail; Engku Muhammad Triyawan, Andy Velayati, Naili Wafa, Faqih El Wahab, Ummi Nurjannah Prastyawati; Abdul Wahjono, Miftahul Husna; Sentot Imam Wahyudi Mardiyati, Hijrah; Mardiyati Wahyuni, Desy Wanci, Muhammad H Holle; Sardin Widiyanto, Hendar Hendar; Siti Mutamimah; Widiyanto WiWitro, DAAA D Wulandari, Muklis Muklis; Risty Yaqin, Ainol Yuliani, Tin Yunus, Muhammad Zakiyah, Rahmatul Huda; Zakiyah Zamzam, Aris

however, need, number, financing, this research, product, product, qard, qard al hasan, regulation, relation, sharia, year, time transaction, for.

- Cluster 3. The blue color consists of 30 items, namely: analysis, bank, data, data collection technology, documentation, effect, financing, income, Indonesia, influence, interview, Islam, Islamic law, object, observation, payment, this research aims, period, population, profit, purposive sampling, Qard financing, research, sample, secondary data, sharia, bank sharia, significant effect, type, value.
- Cluster 4. The yellow color consists of 18 items, namely: customer, difficulty, factor, field research, financial institution, implementation, increase, installment, Islamic bank, lacks, lks, member, practice, Qard contract, qualitative research, researcher, service, solutions.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Implementation of the Qard Agreement

literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 11 research topics regarding the implementation of Qard contracts in Islamic Financial Inclusion, namely:

First, Sharia Financial Institutions. Sharia Financial Institutions can apply the Qard concept by providing Qard-based financing products to their customers. Customers who need funds can apply for a Qard loan from this financial institution. The financial institution will provide the loan without charging interest, but the customer must return the amount lent in accordance with the agreed agreement. The application of Qard in sharia financial institutions is an alternative that is in accordance with Islamic financial principles which prohibit interest.

Second, the Hajj bailout fund. Hajj bailout funds are funds provided by the government or financial institutions to help prospective Hajj pilgrims finance their Hajj pilgrimage. The application of Qard to Hajj bailout funds can mean that the funds given to prospective Hajj pilgrims are a form of interest-free loans that must be repaid after they return from the Hajj pilgrimage. In this way, prospective Hajj pilgrims can use these funds to meet their Hajj travel expenses, while the institutions providing the funds still maintain sharia financial principles which prohibit interest.

Third, the trader environment. The application of Qard in a trader's environment can refer to loans given by traders to fellow traders in the form of Qard hasan (loans that must be returned well) or Qard maruf (loans that can be returned voluntarily). In a trading environment, Qard can be a tool that helps strengthen cooperation and mutual assistance between traders. For example, if a trader needs capital to improve his business, other traders in the neighborhood can provide interest-free Qard loans as a form of support. Traders who receive the loan are then expected to return the loan amount after making a profit from their business.

Fourth, gold pawn transactions. In gold pawning transactions, the implementation of a Qard contract can occur when someone needs a loan and uses gold as collateral. Lenders, such as Islamic financial institutions or pawnshops, provide Qard loans to loan recipients using gold as collateral. Pawned gold is not sold, but kept as collateral for the loan. The loan recipient must return the Qard loan along with the amount due in accordance with the agreed agreement. If the loan recipient cannot repay the loan, the lender has the right to sell the mortgaged gold to pay off the debt.

Fifth, financing of MSMEs (Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises). In MSME financing, the implementation of the Qard contract can be done by providing Qard loans to MSMEs that need capital to develop their business. Lenders, such as Islamic financial institutions or Islamic microfinance institutions, provide interest-free loans to MSMEs. The MSMEs then return the loan in accordance with the agreed agreement. In this case, the loan recipient is responsible for returning the loan without interest, and this is in accordance with sharia financial principles which prohibit interest.

Sixth, sharia insurance. In sharia insurance, the implementation of the Qard contract can occur in the context of tabarru funds (donation funds) which are used to help participants who experience losses. Insurance participants pay contributions or premiums to the sharia insurance company, and these funds are used to pay claims from participants who experience losses. Basically, the premium paid by participants is a form of donation or Qard to the sharia insurance company. If a participant experiences a loss, the insurance company uses tabarru funds to help the participant in accordance with the terms agreed in the sharia insurance contract.

Seventh, education bailout fund products. In educational bailout products, the Qard agreement can be implemented by providing loans to individuals or families to finance education. In a Qard contract, the lender provides funds to the borrower without adding interest or other benefits. Borrowers are expected to return the loan amount according to the specified agreement. The aim of this product is to support wider access to education and provide opportunities for individuals in need to obtain quality education.

Eighth, social function. In the context of social functions, Qard contracts can be used to help individuals or groups who need financial assistance in emergency situations or in facing economic difficulties. Through a Qard contract, lenders can provide funds to borrowers without expecting financial benefits. Borrowers are expected to repay the loan once they are financially capable. The Qard agreement in social functions aims to help others and strengthen solidarity in society.

Ninth, transfer of financing. In transferring financing, a Qard contract can be used as an alternative in situations where the party who needs financing experiences difficulty in paying their financial obligations. For example, if someone is unable to pay a loan provided by a financial institution, the institution may consider replacing the loan with a Qard contract. In this case, the financial institution provides funds as an interest-free loan to the borrower, and the borrower is expected to return the amount according to the agreed agreement. The Qard agreement in the transfer of financing aims to help borrowers overcome their financial difficulties in a more sustainable and fair way.

Tenth, mustahik zakat asnaf gharimin. The Qard contract can be applied in the context of mustahik zakat asnaf gharimin to help those who are classified as poor people who are in debt. In a Qard contract, the lender provides loans to mustahik zakat without charging interest or additional profits. These loans are given with the aim of helping zakat mustahik to pay off their urgent debts. Zakat mustahik are expected to return the loan in accordance with the agreed agreement. The Qard contract in this case aims to help zakat mustahik overcome their financial downturn and reduce the debt burden.

Eleventh, sharia fintech lending platform. Sharia fintech lending platforms are digital financial platforms that offer financing services based on sharia principles. In this context, the Qard contract can be used as a form of

contract in loan transactions between lenders and borrowers. These fintech platforms can adopt Qard contracts by providing loans to borrowers without charging interest or additional profits. Borrowers are expected to repay the loan according to a predetermined agreement.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Influence of the Qard Agreement

literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 8 research topics regarding the influence of Qard contracts on Islamic Financial Inclusion, namely:

First, company profitability. In a Qard contract, the company provides a loan to another party without charging interest. In this case, the company will not gain direct benefits from the Qard contract itself. However, the Qard contract can affect the company's image and reputation in a business environment based on sharia principles. In the long term, a good reputation can attract customers and business partners who are in line with sharia principles, thereby increasing the company's overall revenue potential and profitability.

Second, the company's total assets. Providing loans through Qard contracts can affect a company's total assets. Even though the Qard contract does not generate direct income, the borrower can use the loan for productive business activities. If the borrower succeeds in generating income from these business activities, they can return the loan to the company. Thus, the company can increase its total assets through loans provided through Qard contracts.

Third, community empowerment. One of the main goals of sharia economics is community empowerment. Qard contracts can provide benefits to people who need interest-free funds, especially those who find it difficult to meet the requirements for obtaining conventional loans. With a Qard agreement, people can gain access to the capital needed to start or develop their business. This can improve the welfare and economic capacity of society as a whole.

Fourth, company value. Qard agreements involving interest-free or very low interest loans can have a positive impact on company value. From a sharia perspective, the practice of interest is considered inconsistent with Islamic principles. By using a Qard contract, companies can demonstrate their commitment to ethical principles in Islam. This can improve the company's reputation in the eyes of shareholders, customers and the general public, which in turn can have a positive impact on company value.

Fifth, the company's net profit. The effect of a Qard contract on a company's net profit depends on several factors, such as the size of the loan, the loan period, and the costs associated with the Qard contract. In an interest-free Qard contract, the company does not need to pay interest, so borrowing costs can be reduced. This can increase the company's net profit due to these cost savings. However, if there are administrative costs or management costs associated with the Qard contract, this can affect the company's net profit.

Sixth, increasing the productivity of MSMEs (Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises). Qard agreements can provide significant benefits in increasing the productivity of MSMEs. MSMEs often have difficulty accessing traditional financing offered by conventional financial institutions due to limited collateral or other reasons. In this context, Qard contracts can be an alternative that allows MSMEs to gain access to the financing they need without having to pay high interest. Thus, MSMEs can use this financing to increase production,

purchase equipment, develop innovation, or expand markets. This increase can have a positive impact on MSME productivity and overall economic growth.

Seventh, poverty alleviation. Qard contracts can play a role in alleviating poverty by providing access to financing to those who are less fortunate. In a Qard contract, the lender does not charge interest or only sets very low interest, thereby minimizing the payment burden for the borrower. This allows low-income individuals or economically vulnerable groups to obtain business capital, meet daily needs, or overcome financial crises. With access to affordable financing, individuals or groups have the opportunity to increase income, develop businesses and reduce poverty levels.

Eighth, inflation. In general, Qard contracts do not directly affect inflation because they do not involve interest mechanisms that can trigger a general increase in prices. However, in practice, when Qard contracts are widely used and become the main alternative in the financial system, there are several factors that need to be considered related to inflation. For example, if the amount of money available in society increases significantly through interest-free loans, this could increase demand for goods and services, which in turn could drive prices up. However, this impact may be more related to changes in the amount of money in circulation and other economic factors than directly related to the Qard contract itself.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Juridical Studies regarding the Qard Agreement

literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 10 research topics regarding the juridical study of Qard contracts in Islamic Financial Inclusion, namely:

First, the Qard agreement is based on the DSN-MUI fatwa. The DSN-MUI fatwa is a legal guideline issued by the DSN-MUI which is the authority in Indonesia in the field of sharia finance. The DSN-MUI fatwa regulates the principles and guidelines for implementing financial transactions based on sharia principles. In the context of Qard contracts, the DSN-MUI fatwa provides guidance on the terms, mechanisms and procedures for implementing loan contracts (Qard) in accordance with sharia principles.

Second, the Qard contract is based on maqashid sharia. Maqashid sharia refers to the goals or purposes of Islamic law. In the context of Qard contracts, maqashid sharia plays an important role in determining the principles that must be adhered to so that Qard transactions comply with Islamic law. Several sharia maqashid that are relevant in Qard contracts include maintaining justice, preventing usury, and promoting public benefit.

Third, the Qard contract is based on Islamic law/school of Islamic jurisprudence. Islamic law is the main basis for determining the rules and principles that apply in Qard contracts. Islamic law prohibits the practice of usury and encourages fairness in financial transactions. In a Qard contract, the party providing the loan (muqrid) provides a loan to the party in need (musta'riq) without determining additional profits (riba). This is in accordance with the principles of Islamic law which prohibits usury.

Fourth, the Qard contract is based on OJK regulations. OJK is the institution responsible for regulating and supervising the financial services sector in Indonesia. OJK regulations regulate the practices and standards that financial institutions must comply with, including in sharia-based financial transactions such as Qard contracts. OJK regulations provide a legal framework that regulates the regulation, implementation and supervision of sharia

financial transactions, including Qard contracts, to ensure compliance with sharia principles and protect the interests of the parties involved.

Fifth, Qard products are backed by gold according to a BI circular. According to a Bank Indonesia (BI) Circular, gold-backed Qard products are one type of financing provided by sharia banks. In this financing, banks provide loans to customers using gold as collateral. Customers will receive the gold as financing, and they must return the amount of gold lent to the bank at the specified time. In this case, the bank does not provide additional benefits or rewards to customers, so there is no element of *riba* (interest) in this transaction.

Sixth, legal construction of Qard Hasan financing in Sharia Financial Institutions. Qard Hasan financing is a form of financing used by sharia financial institutions. In its legal construction, Qard Hasan is the provision of loans by financial institutions to customers without any additional profit or compensation requirements that must be paid by the customer. The loan is given with good intentions (*hasan*) and generosity from the lender. Customers are expected to return the loan in the same amount and at the agreed time. In the context of sharia financial institutions, Qard Hasan is a financing instrument that complies with sharia principles.

Seventh, the concept of Qard law in Islamic law/*fiqh*. In Islamic law or *fiqh*, Qard is a form of transaction or contract used in financing. Qard can simply be interpreted as a loan or gift of something to another person with the hope of returning it at a specified time. The legal concept of Qard is based on the principles of justice, mutual assistance and *ukhuwah* (brotherhood) in Islam. In Qard, the party providing the loan is expected to help other people in need, without expecting additional rewards or profits from the loan.

Eighth, the law on taking advantage of Qard contracts regarding the practice of social gatherings. In Islamic law, taking advantage of Qard (loan) agreements in the practice of social gatherings for money has several perspectives that need to be considered. In general, the practice of cash gatherings is considered not to be in accordance with Qard principles, because in cash gatherings there is an element of profit (additional rewards) that the social gathering participants get in turn. This can be categorized as usury (interest) in Islam, because *arisan* participants get additional benefits without contributing or doing equivalent work. Therefore, the practice of social gathering for money is usually not recommended in Islamic law. However, each situation needs to be assessed contextually and based on relevant religious authorities to arrive at a more accurate decision.

Ninth, the DSN-MUI fatwa in the Qard agreement according to the Islamic school of jurisprudence. The DSN-MUI fatwa in the context of the Qard agreement, which is a loan agreement in Islamic law, refers to the legal guidelines and explanations provided by the DSN-MUI. According to *fiqh* (Islamic legal science) from different schools of thought, including the Shafi'i, Hanafi, Maliki, and Hanbali schools, a Qard contract is a loan agreement in which the party who borrows (*muqtarid*) is given property by the party who lends (*muqtaridu*). The assets must be returned in the same amount with no additions or compensation in the form of interest. The DSN-MUI fatwa on Qard contracts generally confirms that Qard practices that do not involve additional or remuneration in the form of interest are in accordance with the principles of *fiqh* of these schools of thought. This fatwa provides guidance for the Muslim community in Indonesia regarding the procedures and conditions that must be fulfilled in carrying out the Qard contract in accordance with Islamic teachings.

Tenth, default on the Qard contract according to the decision of the high religious court. Default in the context of a Qard contract refers to a violation or failure to fulfill the obligations stipulated in the loan agreement. The decision of the High Religious Court is a decision issued by a court institution in Indonesia which has jurisdiction over religious law cases, including cases related to the Qard contract. If there is a breach of contract in the Qard contract, the aggrieved party has the right to file a lawsuit with the religious court. The decision of the High Religious Court in the case of breach of contract of Qard contract will determine whether the violation that occurred meets the legal requirements to be considered a breach of contract. The legal consequences that may be imposed by a religious court on a party who defaults on a Qard contract may include an obligation to return the loan in full, pay fines or losses determined by the court, or other sanctions in accordance with the laws and provisions applicable in the religious justice system. It is important to note that the court decision in each case of breach of Qard contract may vary depending on the facts and law in each case.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Efforts to Develop Qard Contracts

literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 4 research topics regarding efforts to develop Qard contracts in Islamic Financial Inclusion, namely:

First, a strategy to increase profits from the Qard contract business. The strategy to increase profits in the Qard contract business is the steps taken to increase profits in the Qard contract business model. Qard contracts are a form of sharia financing where the lender provides a loan to the loan recipient without charging interest. Profit increasing strategies in this context may involve various approaches, such as increasing lending volume, optimizing capital use, reducing credit risk, expanding market reach, or developing products related to Qard contracts.

Second, promotion of Qard Hasan contract products. Promotion of Qard Hasan contract products refers to efforts to market and promote products that use the Qard Hasan contract. The Qard Hasan contract is a form of Qard contract in the sharia financial system where the borrower is asked to repay the loan without additional costs or compensation to the lender. Promotion of this product can be carried out through various marketing channels such as advertising, exhibitions, social media campaigns, or through relevant business partners.

Third, hybrid contracts on gold-backed Qard products. Hybrid contracts on gold-backed Qard products refer to a combination or combination of Qard contracts (interest-free loans) and other contracts related to gold. In this context, gold-backed Qard products are a form of sharia financing where gold is used as collateral or collateral. Hybrid contracts on this product may include elements such as a sale and purchase agreement, rental agreement, or profit sharing agreement combined with a Qard contract in one product.

Fourth, strengthening the micro sector in Qard financing. Strengthening the micro sector towards Qard financing refers to efforts to strengthen support and development of Qard financing in the micro sector. In this context, the micro sector includes small and micro businesses that need access to financing that is easy and in accordance with sharia principles. This strengthening can involve steps such as training and education for micro business actors, providing access to capital networks, developing products and services that suit the needs

of the micro sector, as well as increasing awareness regarding the benefits and procedures of Qard financing among micro business actors.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Public Perceptions of the Qard Agreement

literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 2 research topics regarding the factors that influence Qard contracts on Islamic Financial Inclusion, namely:

First, the perception of kyai and NU figures regarding the Qard agreement. Perceptions of kyai and NU figures regarding the Qard agreement. They see the Qard contract as a form of generosity and social solidarity that helps the community without involving the practice of usury or interest.

Second, people's interest in making Qard contracts. People's interest in entering into a Qard contract varies depending on factors such as access to formal financial institutions, economic conditions, and understanding of religion. Some people are interested in entering into a Qard contract because they want to avoid the practice of usury and interest which is contrary to the principles of their religion. Social and cultural norms can also influence people's interest in entering into the Qard contract. This interest can be influenced by their understanding of Qard, the availability of other alternatives, and related government regulations.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Factors that Influence Public Interest in the Qard Contract

literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 5 research topics surrounding the factors that influence public interest in Qard contracts in Islamic Financial Inclusion, namely:

First, religiosity/shariah. People's religiosity or sharia can be a significant factor in influencing their interest in the Qard contract. If people have a high commitment to religious teachings and prioritize compliance with sharia principles, they tend to be more interested and motivated to use the Qard Agreement as an alternative financing that is in accordance with their beliefs.

Second, product. The quality and diversity of products offered through Akad Qard can influence public interest. If the products offered are relevant to their needs and desires, and provide clear added value, people tend to be more interested in using the Qard Agreement as a source of financing.

Third, location. Location factors can also influence people's interest in the Qard Agreement. If the nearest financial institution or Akad Qard provider is within easy reach, people will be more likely to consider and utilize the service. Ease of access and convenience in transactions can be important considerations for public interest.

Fourth, promotion. Effective promotional efforts can increase public interest in the Qard Agreement. If information about the benefits and advantages of Akad Qard is presented clearly and interestingly, the public will have a better understanding of the product. Appropriate promotion can increase public awareness and help them recognize the values offered by Akad Qard.

Fifth, service. The quality of services provided by institutions or Qard Akad providers can also influence public interest. Friendly, professional and efficient service will provide a positive experience for the community. If people are satisfied with the services provided, they are more likely to choose Akad Qard as a financing option.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research on Other Issues Related to the Qard Contract

literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 13 research topics surrounding other issues related to Qard contracts in Islamic Financial Inclusion, namely:

First, the Qard agreement in theory and reality. In theory, the Qard contract is considered a simple and easy to implement contract, where the lender gives a certain amount of money or goods to the loan recipient, which must be returned within the agreed time period without any additional benefits (riba). However, in reality, there are several aspects that need to be considered in implementing the Qard contract. For example, it is important to establish clear terms regarding the loan amount, repayment period, and the rights and obligations of both parties. Apart from that, in practice, Qard contracts are often used by sharia financial institutions to provide financing to customers who need interest-free funds, such as consumer financing or business capital.

Second, dispute resolution in the Qard contract. In a Qard contract, disputes can arise between the lender and the loan recipient regarding the implementation of the contract or the return of the loan. To resolve disputes in Qard contracts, generally an attempt is made to reach deliberation (consensus) between the two parties. The goal is to find a solution that is mutually beneficial and fair. If deliberations are unsuccessful, then the parties involved in the dispute can submit a settlement through arbitration or sharia court. Arbitration is usually carried out by mutual agreement to resolve disputes before an independent arbitrator or arbitration institution. Meanwhile, the sharia court is a dispute resolution forum that refers to sharia law and is run by sharia judges who have authority in sharia financial matters.

Third, the problem of implementing Rahn financing with a Qard agreement. Rahn financing is a form of financing in the sharia financial system that uses collateral as a substitute for interest. In the context of Qard contracts, Rahn financing often faces several problems in its implementation. One of the problems that arises is determining the value of the collateral (rahn) used as collateral for financing. Inappropriate appraisal or a decrease in the value of the collateral during the financing period can result in an imbalance between the financing value and the collateral value. Apart from that, other problems that may arise are related to the management of collateral (rahn) during the financing period. The party providing financing needs to ensure that the guarantee is maintained and insured (if necessary) so that the risk of loss can be minimized.

Fourth, the principle of caution in Qard contracts. The principle of prudence in the Qard contract refers to the obligation of the parties involved to be careful and think carefully before carrying out a loan transaction. This principle emphasizes the importance of risk assessment and understanding the financial condition and repayment capacity of loan recipients. In a Qard contract, the lender is expected to assess the eligibility of the loan recipient before providing a loan. This involves evaluating the loan recipient's ability to repay the loan in accordance with the agreed agreement. Loan recipients are also responsible for ensuring that they are able to carry out loan repayment obligations in a timely manner.

Fifth, the principle of ta'awun in Qard contracts in Sharia Financial Institutions. The principle of ta'awun refers to the concept of mutual assistance and cooperation in Islam. In the context of Qard contracts in sharia financial institutions, this principle leads to a spirit of mutual assistance between the lender (muqarrij) and the loan recipient (mustaqir). This ta'awun principle

ensures that the Qard contract is carried out with good intentions and a spirit of mutual assistance, where the lender provides a loan without expecting additional profits or interest.

Sixth, the Qard contract is a tabarru' contract. The Qard contract is a type of tabarru' contract in sharia finance. Tabarru' refers to the principle of voluntary giving and sincerity in providing benefits or donations to others without expecting equal compensation. In a Qard contract, the lender provides a loan to the loan recipient voluntarily without expecting excessive rewards. This contract is based on intentions of kindness and mutual assistance among Muslims.

Seventh, the method of providing for bad debts for Qard products. In the context of Qard products in sharia financial institutions, there is the possibility that there will be receivables that are uncollectible or difficult to repay by the loan recipient. Therefore, Islamic financial institutions implement the method of providing for bad debts as a preventive measure. This method involves establishing a reserve or provision in the financial statements to address the risk of bad debts. This reserve is used to cover possible losses due to unrecoverable receivables.

Eighth, legal protection for the implementation of Qard loan agreements. Legal protection for the implementation of Qard loan agreements is provided by sharia law. Sharia law provides a framework and guidelines for Islamic financial institutions in drafting and implementing Qard loan agreements. Sharia principles which include justice, validity and compliance with Islamic rules are the basis for ensuring the implementation of Qard agreements that are fair and in accordance with the provisions of Islamic law. If a dispute or violation occurs in the implementation of the Qard agreement, the parties involved can apply for a settlement through a court institution that refers to sharia law.

Ninth, return of Qard loans at Sharia Financial Institutions. In principle, Qard is the provision of a loan with the condition that the principal amount of the loan be returned without additional interest. In the context of Sharia Financial Institutions, repayment of Qard loans is carried out in accordance with the terms agreed between the lender (Sharia Financial Institution) and the loan recipient. Usually, Sharia Financial Institutions will determine the term and payment mechanism for Qard loans, which can be in the form of installments or lump sum payments. Loan recipients are expected to comply with the agreement and repay the loan in accordance with the stipulated conditions.

Tenth, the difference between wadi'ah and Qard savings. Wadi'ah savings is a sharia financial product where customers deposit funds with a bank or sharia financial institution to be safeguarded and maintained safely. The bank acts as a fund manager and has the obligation to return all deposited funds to customers. In this case, the customer as the owner of the funds is not entitled to profits resulting from managing these funds. Qard, on the other hand, is a form of loan where the party in need can borrow money from a sharia financial institution or other party with the obligation to return the principal amount of the loan provided without additional interest. In Qard, the party giving the loan does not expect a profit from the loan. The main difference between wadi'ah and Qard savings lies in the rights and obligations of the parties involved. In wadi'ah savings, the customer as the owner of the funds has the right to return the deposited funds in full, while in Qard, the loan recipient has the obligation to return the loan amount given. In addition, in wadi'ah savings, the bank acts as

a manager of funds and can use them for sharia investment activities, while in Qard, the party giving the loan is not entitled to profits from the loan.

Eleventh, the difference between the Wakalah bil Ujrah and Qard contracts in the matter of goods purchase contracts. Wakalah bil Ujrah is a form of wakalah (trust) agreement in which the party who requires services enters into an agreement with a representative to carry out certain actions in exchange for a fee or honorarium. In the context of goods purchase contracts, Wakalah bil Ujrah can be used when an individual wants to buy goods but cannot do so directly. The individual can submit a request to the representative to purchase goods on his or her behalf in exchange for a previously agreed fee or honorarium. On the other hand, Qard is an interest-free loan where the loan recipient is responsible for returning the loan amount provided. In the context of purchasing goods, Qard is not directly related to the contract to purchase goods, because Qard is only related to providing loans of money without additional interest.

Twelfth, land use as collateral for Qard practices. In Qard practice, land can be used as collateral or collateral for loans provided by sharia financial institutions or other parties. If the loan recipient cannot repay the loan according to the agreement, the lender has the right to take ownership of the land used as collateral. However, it should be noted that the use of collateral or collateral in Qard practices can vary depending on the regulations and policies of the Islamic financial institution providing the loan. The practice of using land as collateral in Qard must be in accordance with sharia principles which regulate aspects of justice and compliance with Islamic law.

Thirteenth, the role of the notary in making the deed of agreement implementing the Qard contract. In the context of making deeds of agreements implementing Qard contracts, the role of a notary can vary depending on the legal system and legal practices applicable in a country or jurisdiction. In general, the notary is responsible for ensuring that the process of making the agreement deed is carried out in accordance with applicable legal provisions. A notary can assist in the process of making a deed of agreement implementing the Qard contract by ensuring that legal requirements are met, including the identity of the parties involved, valid agreements, and other relevant provisions. The notary can also provide the necessary witnesses to validate the agreement. It is important to note that the role of a notary in drawing up a deed of agreement implementing a Qard contract may vary depending on legal practices in each country or jurisdiction.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 7 mapping research topics using literature studies regarding Qard contracts in Islamic Financial Inclusion, namely: (1) Application of Qard contracts; (2) The influence of the Qard contract; (3) Juridical study of Qard contracts; (4) Efforts to develop the Qard contract; (5) Public perception of the Qard contract; (6) Factors that influence public interest in the Qard contract; and (7) Other issues related to the Qard contract.

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